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A STUDY OF DIFFERENT TYPES OF ATTACKS ON WIMAX NETWORKS

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Abstract

Wimax is one of the fast growing technologies in the world as compared to other wireless networks. IEEE has defined standard IEEE 802.16 for Wimax. Wimax is growing rapidly due to services it provides and long range accessibility, but still Wimax is facing a lot of security issues and threats like jamming, DDOS, Rogue Base station attack, Reply Attack and so on. Wimax furnish different security mechanism for unauthorized access, Encryption, Authentication etc. and several security architecture, mechanism are proposed. But still Wimax is under attack like Rogue Base station Attack and Reply Attack. In this paper the author has tried to analyze all those attacks in order to develop the security strategies in the future research work.

Keywords: IEEE 802.16, WiMAX, wireless network, threat analysis, vulnerabilities analysis, security, network security,

LITERATURE REVIEW:

L. Wei-min et al., (2008) WiMAX security has two goals, one is to provide privacy across the wireless network and the other is to provide access control to the network. This paper analyzes the physical layer threat and MAC layer threat of WiMAX, and then lists the security requirements of a WiMAX system. Furthermore, we propose the security architecture of WiMAX. In conclusion, we introduce RSA, EAP and HMAC authentication scheme in detail.

M. Habib et al., (2009) have examined the threats which are associated with MAC layer and physical layer of WiMAX and also proposes some enhancements to the existing model for improving the performance of the encryption algorithm. The paper proposes some techniques in the existing model to enhance its functionality and capability. Simulation is done using Qualnet4.5 simulation tool. In the model which is proposed by author, the Security associations are the same as of existing model.

S.S. Hasan et al., (2009) have given an overview of the various kinds of threats in WiMAX i.e. Physical Layer and MAC Layer threats. 2 types of Physical layer threats are discussed here: Jamming and Scrambling. Jamming can be brought about by the introduction of a strong enough noise to substantially reduce the capacity of the channel. Scrambling is a sort of a jamming but for short intervals of time. It is targeted to specific frames or parts of frames.

R.K. Jha et al., (2011) presented simulation of WiMAX based system under jamming. The performance of the system was found out to greatly differ with the use of different jamming signals. Single carrier jamming and multi-carrier jamming were discussed in the paper. OPNET MODELER 14.5 was the software used for the simulation purpose. He tested BER (Bit error rate) vs. simulation time for different antenna used at receiver side under jamming effect.

M. Patidar et al., (2012) presented the WiMAX PHY layer model using simulink of the different modulation schemes. This model gives an impression about the transmission power required for different modulation in the WiMAX system for BER.

INTRODUCTION

The WiMAX Forum website provides a list of certified devices. However, this is not a complete list of devices available as certified modules are embedded into laptops, MIDs (Mobile Internet devices), and other private labeled devices.

Network Layer
MAC Convergence Sublayer
MAC Layer
MAC Privacy Sublayer
PHY Layer

Figure: WiMAX Protocol Stack

Similarly with the PHY layer, the MAC layer allows flexible allocation of transmission capacity to different users. Variably sized MPDUs from different flows can be included into one data burst before being handed over to the PHY layer for transmission. Multiple small MSDUs can be aggregated into one MPDU and, conversely, one big MSDU can be fragmented into multiple small ones in order to further enhance system performance. For example, by bundling up several MPDUs or MSDUs, the PHY and MAC layer header overheads, respectively, can be reduced.

Unfortunately, the IEEE 802.16d has some real problems resultants of the amendments that have been done to produce the new standard i.e. the IEEE 802.16e that can provide some good features for mobile WiMAX. Figure shows WiMAX network which can be used with different devices .The WiMAX and the Wi-Fi can be interoperable to make a large network of communication.

WiMAX Networks

WiMAX can serve as a connection to the public wireless network. It uses optical fiber, microwave link cable or any other elevated speed connectivity. Furthermore, WiMAX uses point to point antennas which join subscriber stations in long distance. Moreover, WiMAX base stations serve many subscriber stations by using Non line of Sight (NLOS) or LOS Point to Multi point connectivity, which could be used both in wired or wireless LAN. Figure below shows the way WiMAX works. It is similar to the cell phone where the user sends and receives data that is called uplink and downlink respectively. WiMAX base station has higher broadcasting power which allows sending and receiving data in long distance. When users want to send data (information) from one or different location, the data will be transferred from one cell to another until the data is received.

Figure - How WiMAX works

EVAALUATION WiMAX SECURITY

In this part, WiMAX security will be discussed to have a clear overview of WiMAX network. WiMAX uses encryption which is a mechanism that provides secured data called data confidentiality and

integrity. Furthermore, WiMAX uses the encryption which means taking the plaintext and mixing the data (information) by applying a complex mathematical algorithm to produce cipher text. The cipher text is transmitted over the wireless network and cannot be understood by the hacker who wants to steal the information. Figure shows WiMAX Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) which is used to create cipher text. The latter can protect the information from any attack that could happen at any moment. Furthermore, AES takes encryption key and uses a counter one as an input to produce and create a bit stream. Finally, the bit stream will be XOR with the plaintext to create the Cipher text as Figure below shows. When the receiver receives the data (information), it will reverse this process to recover the plaintext. However, to activate this process, the transmitter and receiver should use the same encryption key.

Figure: AES Encryption

Moreover, WiMAX uses public key infrastructure and the 802.16e standard of WiMAX that uses version 2 which is (PKMv2). This version provides a good privacy and key management protocol. In addition, PKMv2 provides data security specially when transferring the key between the base station and mobile station. Also, this version identifies the users and whether the data is valid or not. Furthermore, it provides an authorization key (AK) which is very important to obtain the encryption key. The PKMv2 uses the Rivest Shamir Adleman (RSA) which is the public key cryptography exchange. Therefore, RSA public key requires identity from the mobile station, which can be the X.509 digital certificate, or uses immediately the subscriber identity module (SIM) card. The X.509 digital certificate contains the MAC address, which the certificate uses for authority. Figure (7) shows the certificate authority that validates the certificate that can identify the user. When the user identity is validated, the WiMAX network uses the public key to generate authorization key and transmit it to the mobile station.

Figure: Public key infrastructure in WiMAX

GENERAL ATTACKS ON WIRELESS NETWORKS

General, attacks on wireless networks may be divided into four basic categories: passive attacks, active attacks, man-in-the middle attacks, and jamming attacks. A passive attack occurs when someone listens to or eavesdrops on network traffic. A passive attack on a wireless network may not necessarily be malicious in nature. They are very difficult to detect. In passive attacks the attacker is not concerned with the routing protocol. It only eavesdrops on the routing traffic and endeavours to get valuable information like node hierarchy and network topology from it. For example, if a route to a particular node is requested more than other nodes, the attacker might predict that the node is important for the operation of the network, and putting it out could bring down the entire network. Even when it is not possible to isolate the precise position of a node, one may be able to determine information about the network topology by analysing the contents of routing packets. This attack is very difficult to detect and prevent.

In active attacks, the aggressor node has to spend some of its energy in order to carry out the attack. Nodes that perform active attacks with the aim of disrupting other nodes by causing network outage are considered to be harmful, while nodes that perform passive attacks with the aim of saving battery life for their own communications are considered to be selfish. The harmful or malicious nodes can change the routing information by modifying, fabricating or impersonating nodes and thereby disrupting the correct functioning of a routing protocol. Once an attacker has gained enough information from the passive attack, the hacker can then launch an active attack against the network. There are a large number of active attacks that a hacker can launch against a wireless network. Some examples of the attacks are Spoofing attacks, Unauthorized access, Flooding attacks etc. Spoofing occurs when a malicious node misrepresents its identity by altering its MAC or IP address in order to mislead the information about the network topology. It can also create routing loops etc.

GENERAL PHYSICAL LAYER ATTACKS

Jamming attack: Jamming is described by M. Barbeau as an attack “achieved by introducing a source of noise strong enough to significantly reduce the capacity of the channel” [Barbeau05]. Jamming can be either intentional or unintentional. It is not difficult to perform a jamming attack because necessary information and equipments are easy to acquire and there is even a book by Poisel [Poisel03] which teaches jamming techniques.

Solutions: According to Michel Barbeau[Barbeau05], we can prevent jamming attack by increasing the power of signals or by increasing the bandwidth of signals using spreading techniques such as frequency spread spectrum (FHSS) or direct sequence spread spectrum (DSS). Furthermore, since it is easy to detect jamming by using radio spectrum monitoring equipment and the sources of jamming are easy to be located by using radio direction finding tools, we can also ask help from law enforcement to stop the jammers.

Scrambling attack: Also described in [Barbeau05], scrambling is a kind of jamming but only provoked for short intervals of time and targeted to specific WiMAX frames or parts of frames at the PHY layer. Attackers can selectively scramble control or management information in order to affect the normal operation of the network. Slots of data traffic belonging to the targeted SSSs can be scrambled selectively, forcing them to retransmit. It is more difficult to perform a scrambling attack than to perform a jamming attack due to “the need, by the attacker, to interpret control information and to send noise during specific intervals” [Barbeau05].

Solutions: Since scrambling is intermittent, it is more difficult to detect scrambling than jamming. Fortunately, we can use anomalies monitoring beyond performance norm (or criteria) to detect scrambling and scramblers.

Water torture attack: According to D. Johnson and J. Walker[Johnson04] , this is also a typical attack in which an attacker force a SS to drain its battery or consume computing resources by sending a series of bogus frames. This kind of attack is considered even more destructive than a typical Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack since the SS which is a usually portable device is likely to have limited resources.

Solutions: To prevent this kind of attack, a sophisticated mechanism is necessary to discard bogus frames, thus avoiding running out of battery or computational resources.

Other threats: In addition to threats from jamming, scrambling and water torture attacks, 802.16 is also vulnerable to other attacks such as forgery attacks in which an attacker with an adequate radio transmitter can write to a wireless channel [Johnson04] . In mesh mode, 802.16 is also vulnerable to replay attacks in which an attacker resends valid frames that the attacker has intercepted in the middle of forwarding (relaying) process.

Solutions: WiMAX has fixed the security flaw of 802.16 by providing mutual authentication to defend these kinds of attacks.

GENERAL LINK LAYER ATTACKS

Unencrypted Management Communication: Almost all the IEEE 802.16 management messages are still sent unencrypted. The IEEE 802.16-2004 standard does not provide any capability to encrypt management messages.

Masquerading threat: By intercepting the management messages an attacker can use the hardware address of another registered device. Once this is successful an attacker can turn a Base Station (BS) into a Rogue Base Station. A rouge WiMAX base station pretends to be a valid base station, and then drops/eliminates all/some of the packets.

Threat due to Initial Network Entry: In IEEE 802.16j-2009 no integrity protection for management messages can be made in case of multicast transmissions and in case of initial network entry by a new candidate node.

GENERAL NETWORK LAYER ATTACKS

The main network-layer operations in MANETs are ad hoc routing and data packet forwarding, which interact with each other and fulfil the functionality of delivering packets from the source to the destination. Routing messages in Ad Hoc routing protocols exchange routing messages between nodes and maintain routing states at each node accordingly. Data packets are forwarded by intermediate nodes along an established route to the destination based on the routing states. Both routing and packet forwarding operations are vulnerable to malicious attacks, leading to various types of malfunction in the network layer. Network-layer vulnerabilities generally fall into one of **two categories: routing attacks and packet forwarding attacks**, based on the target operation of the attacks.

In the context of DSR, the attacker may modify the source route listed in the RREQ or RREP packets by deleting a node from the list, switching the order of nodes in the list, or appending a new node into the list. In AODV are used, the attacker may advertise a route with a smaller distance metric than its actual distance to the destination, or advertise routing updates with a large sequence number and invalidate all the routing updates from other nodes. By attacking the routing protocols, the attackers

can pull traffic toward certain destinations in the nodes under their control, and cause the packets to be forwarded along a route that is not the optimal route or which may even be nonexistent. The attackers can also create routing loops in the network. Attacks may be launched in addition to routing attacks such as in packet forwarding operations. These attacks do not disrupt the routing protocol but poison the routing states at each node. Instead, they cause the data packets to be delivered in a way that is intentionally inconsistent with the routing states. The attacker may drop or modify the contents of the packets or duplicate the packets it has already forwarded. Attacker may also inject large amount of bogus packets into the network which wastes a significant portion of the network resources and introduces severe wireless channel contention and network congestion in the MANET.

Routing protocols for ad-hoc networks are based on the assumption that intermediate nodes do not maliciously change the protocol fields of messages passed between nodes. This assumed trust permits malicious nodes to easily generate traffic subversion and denial of service (DoS) attacks. Attacks using modification are generally targeted against the integrity of routing computations and so by modifying routing information an attacker can cause network traffic to be dropped, redirected to a different destination, or take a longer route to the destination increasing communication delays. Forged routing packets may be sent to other nodes to divert traffic to the attacker or to some other node. The intention is to create a black hole by routing all packets to the attacker and then discarding it. As an extension to the black hole, an attacker could build a grey hole, in which it intentionally drops some packets but not others, for example, forwarding routing packets but not data packets. A more subtle type of modification attack is the creation of a tunnel (or wormhole) in the network between two colluding malicious nodes linked through a private network connection.

A brief description of the attacks is as follows –

Blackhole Attack: In networking, black holes refer to places in the network where incoming traffic is silently discarded (or "dropped"), hiding from the source the information that the data did not reach its intended recipient. The black holes themselves are invisible, and can only be detected by monitoring the lost traffic. An attacker creates forged packets to impersonate a valid mesh node and subsequently drop packets. The properties of Blackhole attack is that firstly, the Blackhole node exploits the ad hoc routing protocol, such as AODV, to advertise itself as having a valid route to a

Fig: Blackhole Attack Source

destination node, even though the route is false, with the intention of intercepting packets. Secondly, the packets are consumed by the Blackhole node. Thirdly, the Blackhole nodes can conduct coordinated attacks.

Greyhole Attack: Grey Hole is a node that can change from behaving correctly to behaving like a black hole so as to avoid detection. Some researchers discussed and proposed a solution to a black hole attack by disabling the ability for intermediate nodes to reply to a Route Reply (RREP) only allowing the destination to reply.

Wormhole Attack: In a wormhole attack, an attacker forwards packets through a out-of-band high quality link and replays those packets at another location in the network. Wormhole attacks depend on a node misrepresenting its location. Hence, location based routing protocols have the potential to prevent wormhole attacks.

Fig: Wormhole Attack

Flooding Attack: In a flooding attack, the attacker targets the target node by flooding in order to congest the network and degrade its performance.

Rushing Attack: In Multicast forwarding a single stream of data is sent to multiple receivers so as to save network bandwidth. A rushing attacker exploits duplicate suppression mechanism by quickly forwarding route discovery packets and hence gaining access to the forwarding group. The goal of this attack is to invade into routing paths. The Multicast routing protocols are targeted which reduce routing overheads. The method is to quickly forward route discovery (control) packets by skipping processing or routing steps.

Jellyfish Attack: In a jellyfish attack the attacker first needs to intrude into the multicast forwarding group. Then data packets forwarding are delayed for some amount of time before forwarding them. This results in significantly high end-to-end delay and thus degrades the performance of real applications. It causes a increase in end –end delay.

Sybil Attack: In a Sybil attack a large numbers of shadow identities are generated and controlled by the malicious parties. Each radio represents a single individual. However the broadcast nature of radio allows a single node to pretend to be many nodes simultaneously by using many different addresses while transmitting.

TRANSPORT LAYER ATTACKS

Transport layer attacks may occur during authentication and securing end-to-end communications which can be rectified through data encryption. The transport layer is responsible for managing end-to-end connections. Two possible attacks in this layer, flooding and desynchronization as in case of sensor networks .

Flooding: By repeatedly make new connection requests until the resources required by each connection may be exhausted, may reach a maximum limit or may lead to memory exhaustion through flooding. In either case, further legitimate requests will be ignored. One proposed solution to this problem is to require that each connecting client demonstrate its commitment to the connection via the solving of a puzzle. The idea is that a connecting client will not needlessly waste its resources creating unnecessary connections. Since an attacker does not likely have infinite resources, it will be impossible for them to create new connections fast enough to cause resource starvation on the serving node. Although these puzzles do include processing overhead, this technique is still more desirable than excessive communication.

Desynchronization: Disruption of an existing connection is referred to as Desynchronization. An attacker may, for example, repeatedly spoof messages to an end host causing that host to request the retransmission of missed frames. This degrades the ability of the end hosts to successfully send and receive data.

SESSION LAYER ATTACKS

In Session Layer attack an attacker attempts to hijack an established TCP session between two computers by guessing the sequence numbers and taking out one of the user. The counterattacks can be using encryption techniques, limiting incoming traffic etc.

Fig. A typical security infrastructure Source

APPLICATION LAYER ATTACKS

Application Layer attacks involve viruses, worms, malicious codes, application abuses etc. When data being transmitted is unencrypted, it is vulnerable to sniffing as well as attacks against applications. Several additional features must be implemented within network equipment to ensure against sniffing of data packets as shown in the figure to provide additional security.

SUMMARY

In this report, security solution, various vulnerabilities and possible attacks to WiMAX network have been discussed and illustrated. The threats apply to both layers of WiMAX. At PHY layers, jamming can be considered a major threat. At MAC layer, critical threats include eavesdropping of management messages, masquerading, management message modification or DoS attacks. Some of these issues have been fixed with the adoption of recent amendments and security solutions in IEEE 802.16 but some still exist and need to be considered carefully. However, through this review, we can see that WiMAX does offer much more strong security solutions in comparison with other wireless technologies such as Bluetooth or Wireless Fidelity (WiFi). WiMAX is still under development and need more research on its securities vulnerabilities. In the near future, when WiMAX achieves a maturity level, it would have a great opportunity to be a successful wireless communication technology.

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